

PIDs

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INRAE
National Research Institute
for Agriculture, Food and
the Environment.

Providing a recommendations document on PIDs usages

Each day, INRAE research teams produce plenty of data concerning animals, plants, landscapes and documents. **All the data, coming from observations and experiences, have to be stored properly, and published to be valued and reused.** It's vital to make this data easily findable, and every data object must be uniquely identified to be potentially cross-referenced with other data produced anywhere in the world.

The main goal of this use case is the **production of a recommendations document on PIDs**, to be adopted and applied in the Institute. The recommendations of different resource types (people, structures, events, sensors, documents and data) should lead research teams to adopt FAIR principles in their data management.

Challenges that need to be addressed

- Composing a recommendations document, which adequately explains what kind of identifier should be used to represent this or that type of data.
- Being as precise as possible to explain how to organise data versioning and identifier versioning, and evolving datasets identification.
- Being very close to today's end-users usages to optimise adoption by research teams

Expected impact of the Use Case

The recommendations document must inform the choice of researchers in the use of this or that PID. It should make it possible to harmonise these choices within the institute.

This document will allow:

- **Researchers & engineers** to implement technical solutions with the help of the recommendations.
- The **Institute** to offer a PID management service guaranteeing their storage and resolution.

Expected outputs

PID management software system offered by the Institute to its research teams.

Contributors

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